

Mapping tree species proportions in boreal forest with Sentinel2 time series data and a convolutional neural network

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Abstract

Tree species is an important characteristic of forests that influences carbon stock change, resilience to climate change, the value of timber resources, and future forest management options. Despite its importance and considerable research efforts, developing reliable, fine-resolution tree species maps still remains challenging. We used weekly time-series of Sentinel-2 satellite images over Norway in convolutional neural network (CNN) and multivariate random forest (RF) models trained on > 10 000 National Forest Inventory field plots to map proportions of spruce, pine and deciduous trees. The models were validated using an independent dataset with > 2000 field reference plots. We also predicted the dominant tree species and analyzed model accuracy under different forest conditions. The CNN models performed better than the RF models and for species proportions the predicted R^2 values were in the range 0.39 – 0.52. Predictions of dominant species resulted in an overall accuracy of 71%. The accuracy of the models was better for mature and older forest with a closed canopy cover than for younger or sparsely stocked forest.

Keywords: Deep learning, random forest, optical satellite, multivariate response, national forest inventory

1. Introduction

Knowledge on the spatial distribution and extent of different tree species represents important information to support sustainable forest management practices aimed at simultaneously meeting objectives of timber production (Haara et al., 2019), biodiversity conservation (Baeten et al., 2019; Barbier et al., 2008), and climate change mitigation (Alvarez et al., 2016; Hof et al., 2017). As such, tree species classification using remotely sensed data has long been studied (Fassnacht et al., 2016). Nowadays, earth observation programs such as Copernicus from the European space agency, provide free access to time series of spaceborne imagery at frequent intervals (i.e. 2-5 days), thus opening up new opportunities to capture the phenological signatures characteristic of different tree species and improve our ability to classify them. Further, rapid advances in machine learning in the sub-domain of deep-learning (LeCun et al., 2015) offer new capabilities to analyze the complexity of dense satellite time series data more efficiently.

In previous studies, tree species classification using freely available, moderate-resolution satellite images has been performed using both single-date and time-series. Zhu and Liu (2014) classified forest types in a humid continental climate consisting of pine, oak and mixed-mesophytic forest in a 1,790 km² study area in the Vinton county of south-eastern Ohio. They used Landsat time-series (five Landsat 5 TM and two Landsat 7 ETM+ images) and the support vector machine classifier. They reported an overall accuracy of 91% on pixel level obtained from a subset of field plots. Immitzer et al. (2019) classified seven broadleaved and conifer tree species in temperate forests in central Europe in two test areas of 100 km² each. Using the Random Forest (RF) classifier (Breiman, 2001) and single date Sentinel-2 images, they obtained an overall cross-validated accuracy of 65%. Immitzer et al. (2019) classified seven broadleaved and five conifer tree species in temperate forests in a 1,056 km² study area in Austria. They used the RF classifier and a Sentinel-2 time series of 18 cloud free images and obtained an 'out-of-bag' overall accuracy for broadleaved and conifer tree species of 86% and 95%, respectively. Persson et al. (2018) classified five tree species in a small study area of approximately 25 km² in central Sweden. Using RF and a Sentinel-2 time series consisting of four images, they reported 88% overall accuracy from cross-validation on pixel-level training data. Breidenbach et al. (2021) used RF to classify the three main tree species (groups) in Norway (Norway spruce, Scots pine, deciduous) using two cloud-free, nation-wide Sentinel-2 mosaics acquired in the spring and summer, the geo-location of sample plots, and old maps on coniferous and deciduous forests. They obtained cross-validated overall accuracies of 74% on plot level and overall accuracies of 90% given independent reference observations on stand level. Hemmerling et al. (2021) classified 17 tree species, with the main species being Scots pine, Norway spruce, larch, Douglas fir, oak, and beech. They used an RF classifier and Sentinel-2 time series of all available Sentinel-2 scenes acquired between January 1st 2018 and December 31st 2019 with an estimated cloud cover of <75%. Their study site comprised 30,000 km² in temperate forests in central Europe (the entire federal state of Brandenburg in Germany). The authors reported an overall accuracy of 96% for stand-wise forest inventory reference data, with most classification errors occurring in small classes corresponding to less-frequent tree species. Grabska et al. (2020) performed an exhaustive analysis of different machine learning algorithms to classify tree species in a fairly complex forest area (i.e. 11 tree species) and found support vector machines to be outperforming (overall accuracy >85%) the alternative methods.

An alternative way to tackle tree species mapping is to model tree species proportions of mixed pixels and consequently use these to define species dominance. Within this domain, the models need to comply with two fundamental constraints: i) the sum of the predicted proportions needs to sum up to one, and ii) the proportions need to be non-negative. Concerning the modeling of tree species proportions, several approaches have been proposed, and early works on the subject include studies by Magnussen (1997) and Hyypä & Törmä (1999). Donoghue et al. (2007) and Vihevaara et al. (2015) proposed the use of logistic and beta regression, respectively. One of the main limitations of these two models is that they allow for the prediction of only two proportions and thus are unsuitable in cases where more than two species are present. To overcome this limitation Puliti et al. (2017) and Ørka et al. (2021) proposed the use of the Dirichlet regression, which allows for the prediction on any given number of proportions. Ørka et al. (2013) proposed an individual-tree-crown segmentation approach to derive single tree basal area and consequently compute plot-level species proportions in terms of basal area from the

aggregated trees. While all of the abovementioned studies used airborne laser scanning, Reese et al. (2002), Wallerman and Holmgren (2007), and Kukkonen et al (2021), adopted a non-parametric K-*nn* method to impute species proportions based on satellite imagery. Even though the predictive accuracy of studies based on satellite data on the dominant species in each study area was lower (relative RMSE 64%-98%) compared to methods based on ALS and multi- or hyperspectral data (relative RMSE 34%-40%), such approaches are more suitable for nationwide monitoring programs as they rely on freely available data. With the advent of deep learning, new possibilities arise to predict species proportions. Bolyn et al. (2022) predicted tree species proportions in forest in the southern part of Belgium using a deep convolutional neural network (CNN) and Sentinel2 in combination with high resolution PlanetScope satellite data. Other studies using deep learning methods for solving tree species classification problems have been conducted using high resolution aerial or satellite images, hyperspectral images, or LiDAR data. Mäyrä et al. (2021) used airborne hyperspectral and LiDAR data using 3D convolutional neural networks in a 83 km² study site in southern Finland dominated by four tree species. The authors reported 87% overall accuracy for the best performing 3D-CNN model for a validation data set of individual tree crowns. Seidel et al. (2021) used image representations of 3D point clouds of individual trees and CNNs for classifying seven tree species in Germany and the US west coast (Oregon). They reported 86% classification accuracy for an independent test data set. Briechle et al. (2021) classified tree species and standing dead trees from combined ALS (image representation) and multispectral remote sensing data using CNNs in two study areas in the temperate climate zone with 0.37 km² and 8.3 km², respectively. They reported 96% and 91% overall accuracy, respectively, for an independent test data set. Zhang et al. (2020) used airborne hyperspectral images and 3D-CNNs for classifying several tree species in a subtropical monsoon climate in a 0.5 km² study area in southern China. They used 95% of their data as an independent test data set and reported 94% classification accuracy of their improved 3D-1D-CNN, which requires less computing resources.

The aim of the current study was to develop nation-wide models for tree species proportions and dominant tree species in the boreal forests of Norway using Sentinel2 time series data. We furthermore wanted to compare predictions from a CNN and a multivariate RF model, and validate the results on an independent dataset. A multivariate RF method which ensures consistency among the response variables was introduced by Ishwaran (2008), and to the best of our knowledge our study is the first to apply this method for prediction of tree species proportions.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Study area

This study was carried out using data from the field plots in the National Forest Inventory (NFI) in Norway (Fig. 1). The forest covered by the field plots used in the present study is boreal, with Norway spruce (*Picea abies*) and Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris*) as the most common species. Birch (*Betula pubescens*) is also present in many locations, and there are more scattered occurrences of other broadleaved species such as rowan (*Sorbus aucuparia*), oak (*Quercus robur*), beech (*Fagus sylvatica*), ash (*Fraxinus excelsior*) and species in the salix family.

Figure 1. Study area and the spatial distribution of the field plots. The permanent NFI field plots (blue) and a set of temporary NFI field plots (red). (The reader is referred to a digital version of this paper for a color map).

2.2 Field data

This study used the permanent, and a subset of the temporary NFI field plots (Breidenbach et al. 2020). The Norwegian NFI consists of a systematic grid of sample plot locations laid out in the whole of Norway (Fig. 1). The distance between plots varies according to the following specification: In the most productive regions, the plots are located on a 3 by 3 km grid. In non-productive and mountainous areas a 9 by 3 km grid is used.

Plots on forested land are visited in the field every fifth year, and a number of measurements and registrations are carried out. The registrations include measurements on all trees with a diameter at breast height (DBH) ≥ 5 cm within a circular 250 m² plot. Several features are recorded for each tree including tree species and DBH. Tree heights are recorded for a subsample of trees on each plot. The 250 m² plots are all positioned using a global navigation satellite system (GNSS). In addition to the permanent NFI plots, additional temporary field plots are measured in selected regions and years. The temporary field plots are measured following the same procedure as the permanent field plots. For this study we used a subset of ~12 400 field plots, summarized in Table 1. The species proportions on each field plot were calculated using the total and per-species stem volumes of all living

trees (with DBH ≥ 5 cm), i.e. the species proportions referred to in this study are the per-species *proportions of the total stem volume*. The distribution of the species proportion over all training and test field plots are given in Figure 2.

The plots measured in 2019 – which corresponded in time with the Sentinel2 data – were selected for the independent test dataset.

Table 1. Summary of the field data. Year of field measurements and number of plots. Mean and median proportions of spruce, pine and deciduous trees on the field plots used for training and test.

	Field year	n	n (dominant species > 75%)	Spruce _{PROP}	Pine _{PROP}	Deciduous _{PR} OP
				mean (median)	mean (median)	mean (median)
Training	2011 – 2020 ¹	10,185	7,660	0.29 (0.01)	0.34 (<0.01)	0.37 (0.17)
Test	2019	2,227	1,689	0.30 (0.01)	0.32 (<0.01)	0.38 (0.17)

¹ Excluding 2019.

Fig 2. Density plots of species proportions for the field plots in the training dataset (left) and the test dataset (right). The figures show that the two datasets have a similar distribution of species proportions.

2.3 Sentinel-2 data

We used Sentinel-2 data acquired in 2019, from between May 1 and September 29, covering the growing season for trees in Norway. All available atmospherically corrected Sentinel-2 (Level-2A) data in the period were initially used, with pixels classified as clouds or snow removed in a first data processing step. Using the classification from Sen2Cor delivered with the data, pixels with scene classification value of 9 – 11, corresponding to *cloud - high probability*, *thin cirrus* and *snow* were discarded from further analysis. In this study we used six spectral bands, namely 2, 3, 4, 8A, 11, and 12. Band 2 – 4 were resampled to a spatial resolution of 20 m, such that all bands had the same resolution. The Sentinel-2 data were organized as pixel-wise time series, arranged as one 2D array for each pixel – with the six bands and time giving the two dimensions. Along the time dimension the spectral values were resampled to weekly values at the pixel level using the following procedure: 1) First all missing values were interpolated along the time dimension, using a linear interpolation between the nearest non-missing value before and after the acquisition date for the missing pixel value. The interpolation was done for each band and pixel separately. 2) The weekly values were then obtained by keeping the median value for each week, separately for each band. The result of this temporal resampling was a representation of the Sentinel-2 data for each pixel consisting of 132 spectral values, given by 6 bands \times 22 weeks. These values can be represented as a 2D array, and depicted as a raster image (Fig. 3). Note that one 6×22 array thus represents the Sentinel-2 time series data for one 20 m pixel in the Sentinel-2 satellite imagery. The method described here corresponds to the method used by Debella-Gilo and Gjertsen (2021).

Figure 3. Example of raster representation of time series arrays corresponding to plots dominated by spruce (top), pine (middle), and deciduous trees (bottom).

2.4 Datasets

Data from Sentinel2 were extracted for the locations of the NFI field plots, and the field and remote sensing data were combined to one dataset for model training, and one separate independent test dataset. Field plots measured in 2019 were used for the test set, and the remaining data were used for model training. The spectral values from the Sentinel2 imagery

were extracted for the 250 m² circular field plots by calculating the weighted mean of the values for the pixels covered by each field plot. The area in each pixel covered by the field plot was used as weight. The resulting two datasets consisted of 10,185 and 2,227 observations for training and test, respectively. Note that for the CNN models, the training dataset was further split into two parts, by convention denoted training and validation datasets. In order to avoid confusion we denote – throughout this study – the separate independent dataset used for the final validation and comparison between the two model types as the *independent test dataset*. For the classification of the dominant species, a subset of 7660 plots of the initial datasets was used in which the dominant species constituted at least 75% of the volume.

2.5 Workflow and models

We applied two different types of models in this study: CNN and multivariate RF. With both types of models we modeled species proportions and dominant tree species using the training dataset described above. The independent test dataset was used only for final validation using the model predictions. A conceptual overview of the study is given in Fig. 4, and the four different models are further described in the following.

Fig. 4. Conceptual workflow of the study.

CNN models

The two CNN models for prediction of species proportions and dominant species were implemented in Python using the Keras sequential framework in Tensorflow (Chollet and others, 2015; Martín Abadi et al., 2015). These models will in the following be denoted CNN_p for species proportions, and CNN_c for classification of dominant species. A summary of the model characteristics is given in Table 2, and a representation of the full structure of the

CNN models is included in appendix A. Similar model structures were applied for the two models CNNp and CNNc with one notable difference: the loss function used as part of the model training. Whereas the CNNc model was trained using a sparse categorical cross-entropy loss function, implemented in the `tensorflow.keras.losses.SparseCategoricalCrossentropy` function (Martín Abadi et al., 2015), the CNNp model was trained using a mean squared error loss function given by

$$\frac{(y_s - \hat{y}_s)^2 + (y_p - \hat{y}_p)^2 + (y_d - \hat{y}_d)^2}{3}, \quad (1)$$

where y_s, y_p and y_d are the field measured proportion of spruce, pine and deciduous trees, respectively. \hat{y}_s, \hat{y}_p and \hat{y}_d are the corresponding predicted proportion of spruce, pine and deciduous trees. In both of the models CNNp and CNNc *softmax* was used as the activation function in the last dense layer. In the case of the CNNp model this ensured that all the output values were positive and summed to one, and were directly used as the predicted tree species proportions at each field plot (i.e. \hat{y}_i). For the CNNc the species with the highest value from the softmax activation function was taken as the predicted dominant tree species. A CNN framework with four convolutional layers was used, and in order to improve the training and avoid overfitting the following processing was applied in connection to each convolution: batch normalization, 2D spatial dropout and addition of Gaussian noise. The spatial dropout was applied using a dropout rate of 0.25, and the Gaussian noise was added using $\sqrt{0.03}$ as the standard deviation of the noise distribution.

The models were trained with the training datasets described above, and for both of the CNN models this dataset was split into a set of 80% of the observations for training and the remaining 20% for validation. This resulted in sets of 8148 and 2037 observations for the CNNp model and 6128 and 1532 observations for the CNNc model. The reference values – or labels – which were used in the training were the species proportion in the case of CNNp, and the class of the dominant species in the case of CNNc. Each of the two models was trained for a maximum of 200 epochs with a batch size of 32. We did monitor the loss during the training, and if the performance of the model did not improve during three consecutive epochs, the training was stopped.

The specific model structure and parameter settings for the CNN models used in this study were derived through a combination of experimentation and suggestions and recommendations in the Tensorflow online documentation.

Table 2. Summary characteristics of the CNN models.

Input dimensions	6 spectral bands × 22 weekly medians
Batch size	32
Number of convolution layers	4
Number of outputs	3
Loss function	CNNc: sparse categorical cross-entropy, CNNp: mean

	squared error (see text for details).
Optimizer	Adam
Learning rate	Initial 0.001, set to decay with training progress
Maximum number of epochs	200

RF models

We compared the predictions from the two CNN models to predictions from corresponding RF models, using the same datasets for training. Following a similar naming convention, the two RF models are denoted RFp and RFc for modeling the species proportions and dominant species classification, respectively.

The RFc were trained using the randomForest package in R (Liaw and Wiener, 2002; R Core Team, 2020), and the RFp were trained using the randomForestSRC package (Ishwaran and Kogalur, 2007) which implements multivariate RF models (Ishwaran et al., 2008). For both RFp and RFc the values for the hyperparameters number of trees (ntrees), number of explanatory variables as candidates for node splitting (mtry), and the minimum number of observations in the final node (nodesize) were set to $ntrees=1,000$, $mtry=p/3$ where p is the number of explanatory variables, and $nodesize=5$. In the case of the RFp the predicted proportions per plot sum to one and are thus consistent without further adjustment.

2.6 Validation and evaluation

We validated the models using an independent test dataset, selected to correspond in time with the acquisition of the Sentinel2 data. Predictions from the models were then compared to species proportions derived from field measurements on the field plots in the test dataset. We evaluated the predicted species proportions directly and for tertiles, i.e. a grouping into low, medium and high proportions. The CNNc and RFc models were trained using only data with a clear domination of one of the species, but the evaluation was done on all field plots in the test dataset. The species with the highest proportion was defined to be the dominating species on the plot.

From the CNNc model we obtained the predicted dominant species, but also the underlying class probability from the softmax layer. We evaluated if this probability could be used as an indicator for the reliability of the predictions.

3. Results

We trained the four models CNNp, CNNc, RFp and RFc following the procedure outlined above. Learning curves from the training of the CNN models are given in Figures 5 and 6. Note that due to the imposed restriction on the number of epochs without improvement in the model performance, the training was stopped before the maximum number of epochs for both models.

The models were then used to predict species proportions and dominant species for the independent test dataset. The predicted values were compared to the field reference values, and the performance of the models assessed.

Using the CNNp model, we created species proportion maps for parts of the study area given in Figure 7.

For the prediction of species proportions the overall performance of the models were moderate, with R2 values of 0.33 – 0.52. The CNN models performed in all cases clearly better than the RF models (Tab. 3, Fig. 8 and Fig. 9). There were only minor differences in accuracy between the species, but a slightly better performance was observed for the prediction of proportion of deciduous trees (Table 3). We also assessed the predictions of species proportions by tertiles, i.e. dividing the proportion of each species into three classes corresponding to a high, medium or low share of the total volume on the plot (Table 4 and Fig. 8). The performance of the models when evaluated for tertiles shows that the best results are obtained when the share of the total volume by one species is either high or low. In mixed forest, where the shares of the total volume are more evenly distributed among several species, the results are poorer (Tab. 4).

Fig 5. Learning curves from the training of the CNNc model. Loss (orange) and accuracy (blue). For training data (solid line) and validation data (dotted line).

Fig 6. Learning curves from the training of the CNNp model. Loss is the mean squared error (see text for details). For training data (solid line) and validation data (dotted line).

Figure 7. Example of map with predicted species proportions (left), and an orthophoto from the same area (right). Proportions of pine, deciduous trees and spruce correspond to the values in the red, green and blue color channel, respectively. (Orthophoto: © norgebilder.no).

Table 3. Summary of the prediction of species proportions in the independent test dataset.

model	species	predicted R^2	RMSE	RMSE%
RFp	spruce	0.36	0.31	102.8

	pine	0.33	0.34	104.4
	deciduous	0.48	0.30	78.4
CNNp	spruce	0.39	0.30	100.5
	pine	0.40	0.32	98.9
	deciduous	0.52	0.29	75.3

Figure 8. Predicted tree species proportions from the CNNp model (top) and the RFP model (bottom). Field measured vs. predicted species proportions in the independent test dataset of Norway spruce (left), Scots pine (middle) and deciduous trees (right). The boxplots show the distribution of predicted proportions for each tertile of the field reference values.

Table 4. Evaluation of predicted species proportion tertiles. Results from prediction with the CNNp model.

Species	Tertile	F1-score	OA
spruce	low	0.83	0.69
	medium	0.26	
	high	0.60	
pine	low	0.84	0.69
	medium	0.15	
	high	0.53	
deciduous	low	0.83	0.74
	medium	0.19	
	high	0.76	

In the comparison of the two models predicting dominant species, the CNNc model performed better than the RFc model, with an OA for the CNNc model of 71 %, and an OA for the RFc of 68 %. Confusion matrices for the validation of the two models are given in Fig. 9. Further model characteristics were explored using the CNNc model. When evaluating the class probabilities of the CNNc model, roughly half of the predictions had associated probabilities larger than 90% and the OA of these was 87%, whereas predictions with lower probabilities had an OA of 57%. This shows that the prediction probabilities are a useful measure to appraise the accuracy of a single prediction. The accuracy was higher in mature and older forest than in young forests (Tab. 5). The accuracy was also higher in closed forests than in sparsely stocked forests (Tab. 5) but no clear pattern in accuracy was visible given different site index classes. Ground (vegetation) reflections are stronger and more likely in young and open forest which might be the reason for the poorer model accuracy. As with the predictions of species proportions, the model performed best in pure forest (OA=82%, n=920) and much worse in mixed forests where no species represented more than 75% of the volume (OA=54%, n=538). The poorer performance in mixed forest is expected, as the difference between the proportion of the species is smaller.

Figure 9. Confusion matrices for predictions of the dominant species in the independent test dataset using the CNNc model (left) and the RFc model (right).

Table 5. Classification accuracy for predictions of dominant tree species in the independent test dataset with the CNNc model. For maturity class (2 = young forest, 5 = mature forest) and tree density.

Maturity class	Tree density	n	OA
2	Normal	113	66
2	Low	26	62
3	Normal	171	81
3	Low	23	74
4	Normal	171	80
4	Low	34	76
5	Normal	425	83
5	Low	110	71

4. Discussion

We have in this study modeled tree species proportions using time series of Sentinel2 satellite data, and compared predictions from CNN and multivariate RF-based models. Overall we obtained moderate accuracy for predictions of species proportions when validating on an independent dataset. We also predicted dominant species, with an OA of 71%.

Bolyn et al. (2022) mapped proportions of nine tree species classes in Belgium, and they report an R^2 of 0.5 for the predicted proportions, and an overall accuracy of 0.73 when classifying the dominant species. The R^2 value is slightly higher than what we obtained, and

the overall accuracy for the dominant species was slightly lower in the current study. Notable differences between the study by Bolyn et al. and ours, are the higher number of species classes, and a much bigger dataset for training. They used > 100 000 forest polygons for training, as well as additional high resolution satellite imagery.

Ørka et al. (2013) predicted species proportions in boreal forest, and obtained R^2 values in the range 0.82 - 0.89. Similar species classes as the current study were used, but the remote sensing data were from airborne laser scanning and hyperspectral imagery.

Puliti et al. (2017) predicted species proportions in boreal forest from photogrammetric point clouds using Dirichlet regression. Species proportions were predicted with RSMEs of 34-42% for spruce, 42-56% for pine, and 75-92% for deciduous trees.

Both Ørka et al. and Puliti et al. obtained higher accuracy than in our study, but they also used remote sensing data with a higher spatial and spectral resolution. This will limit the application of those methods to areas where this type of data is available.

Breidenbach et al. (2021) predicted dominant tree species using Sentinel2 data and reference data from the Norwegian NFI, and is therefore directly comparable to the prediction of dominant species in the current study. In the study by Breidenbach et al. a combination of satellite data from two time points gave an OA of 78.6% for predictions of the dominant species. This is slightly higher than in the current study, and suggest that the inclusion of additional Sentinel2 data in the current study did not contribute substantial information with respect to the dominant species, or, the methods we applied in the current study were not able to utilize this added information.

We have in this study used the CNN model structure described in section 2.5 and in appendix A. Other CNN model structures could have been applied, but the limited size of the training dataset will be a constraint on the complexity of any CNN model used with this dataset. Several approaches could be taken to overcome this: The size of the training data could be extended with additional field reference data, or a pre-trained deep learning model such as a geospatial foundation model (Jakubik et al., 2023) or YOLO (Jocher et al., 2023) could be applied. This could be subject to further research.

2D convolution is typically applied to images where the pixels have a clear spatial relationship with their neighboring pixels, but in the current study the relationship between neighboring pixels is not as strong as in conventional images. In the time dimension of the rasters used in this study, the relationship stems from the fact that the values are adjacent in time, but the relationship is weaker in the spectral dimension. We will however argue that since the spectral information in the input rasters are ordered according to wavelength, there is also a relationship between neighboring pixels in the spectral dimension. The application of 2D convolution could however have an effect on the performance of the models, and adjustments to how convolution is applied in the model could be subject to further investigations.

5. Conclusions

The results from this study show that species proportions in boreal forest can be predicted using Sentinel2 satellite time series with moderate accuracy. Predicting the dominant species resulted in an OA of 71% which is slightly lower than in comparable previous studies where the dominant species was predicted using Sentinel2 satellite imagery.

We found that the models based on CNN performed better than the multivariate RF-based models.

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Funding

Funding for this study was provided by the Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research (NIBIO), project no. 52280.

Declaration of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interests.

Appendix A. A graphical representation of all layers in the two CNN models used in the study.

